

Title: Daylight Saving Time and Mortality—Proceed with Caution

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Disclosure: (i) Dr. Klerman: consulting for American Academy of Sleep Medicine Foundation, Circadian Therapeutics, National Sleep Foundation, Sleep Research Society Foundation. Yale University Press; partner owns Chronsulting. (ii) Dr. Weaver: Consulting: Fred Hutchinson Cancer Center, National Sleep Foundation, University of Pittsburgh. (iii) Dr. Roenneberg: founder and CSO of Chronsulting UG (iv) Dr. Malow: Dr. Malow: consultant to Neurim Pharmaceuticals. (v) Dr. Johnson: a member of Board of Directors of Save Standard Time, a volunteer run nonprofit supporting permanent standard time, a member of the American Academy of Sleep Medicine Advocacy committee supporting permanent standard time. Dr. Johnson has no financial disclosures.

Author contributions: All authors contributed to the conceptualization, writing, and editing of the article.

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The article “*Daylight saving time affects European mortality patterns*” by Levy et al.¹ reports associations between all-cause mortality and multiple factors, including the clock time changes between standard time [ST] and daylight saving time [DST] in spring and fall, using data from 1998 to 2012 in 16 European countries. While the abstract reports that mortality decreases for two weeks after the spring change and shows a reverse effect in the fall, their Figure 1b/c clearly shows the opposite in the weeks after the transition: a relative *increase* from already decreasing mortality trend after the spring change and a relative *decrease* from the already increasing trend in the fall. The authors base their abstract text on the outcome of a multiple negative binomial regression model. Here, we suggest major flaws in the statistical model and conclusions. In addition, the title and conclusions suggest that the findings can be linked to long-term DST effects; this misattribution may lead people to believe these data inform the choice between permanent DST or permanent ST- which they should not.

The data in their Figure 1 are consistent with multiple previous reports²⁻⁴, including some listed in the source article. We agree that analyses need to be adjusted for relevant covariates. However, why does their regression model (their Table 1) reverse the direction of the results from their Figure 1? We present four likely reasons:

- Severe collinearity in the statistical model. The most relevant collinear parameters used are season, month, DST transition weeks, a sinusoid representing photoperiod, temperature, and humidity. All of these parameters are interdependent, yet there is no mention of testing for collinearity and adjusting the model appropriately.
- Their Table 1 is an excellent (though not exhaustive) compilation of parameters that are associated with mortality rates. Since the stated focus of this article is whether DST transitions are associated with changes in mortality rates, the statistical model used is not correct. An appropriate model would need to test whether the parameters listed in Table 1 affect mortality rates associated with the DST transitions (e.g., whether the observed results are only specific for a given year or whether the age or sex composition differs before and after DST clock transitions).
- Since the research question is about mortality associated with DST transitions, the dataset should only include weeks of data before and after those transitions, not the entire time series. This smaller dataset could be used with fewer covariates. Note that the authors describe the relevant time as 2 months before and after the DST clock transitions, yet the model includes data from throughout the year.
- Although the paper’s Figure 1 shows data from 2 months before and after the DST changes, the statistical model’s comparison for DST results is based on a single week before the changes, which is not appropriate given the longer-term seasonal trends in the data (e.g., rising in fall, falling in spring). These trends alone cause the mortality to be lower in the spring and higher a few weeks in the fall after the comparison week— as is found using this statistical model. This method does not unveil the independent effect of DST transitions. When a comparison is made vs. this trend (as in Figure 1b/c), the opposite change in mortality rates is seen. Therefore, incorporating seasonal trends explicitly is critical – e.g., through an Interrupted Time Series design to test a change in slope. Of note, the Table listings

are out-of-order in that week 0 is before week -1 (i.e., the order is 0,-1,1,2,3,4,...) for both fall and spring groupings.

Other considerations:

- The model is constructed to include many parameters potentially associated with mortality risk and report the relative importance of each. The incidence rate ratio (IRR) reported as statistically significant for the spring is 0.97 (weeks 1 and 2) and for the fall is 1.02 (weeks 1, 2) - and, contrary to their conclusions, 0.98 in week 0 and 0.97 in week 4. These differences probably reflect the variation in the data. Any statistical significance for effects of this size is likely achieved due to the massive sample size. While even one excess death is too many, the relative impact of DST transitions in this analysis is very low. The IRR for other metrics are similar (e.g., daily humidity) or much higher (e.g., year, month, age, country). These other statistically significant factors do not receive the same emphasis by authors – including the title of the paper. In addition, more commonly used adjustments for multiple comparisons would render the primary finding as mixed or non-significant (Bonferroni p-value=0.0006), despite the robust sample size.
- Since the reason for deaths is not reported, no distinction can be made between deaths expected to be related to DST transitions (e.g., traffic accidents) vs. those that have longer-term determinants (e.g., cancer).
- As noted above, the IRR reported using the multiple negative binomial regression model are inconsistent with multiple other studies of health effects associated with DST transitions. The spring ST->DST transition is associated with increases in the most common causes of death - heart attacks² and strokes.⁴
- Even without the potential statistical issues mentioned above, the over-extension of these results (of weeks after each transition) to claim that DST (which is present for many months of the year) affects mortality is not supported and should not be included in the title or in the discussion.

In addition to the short-term adverse health effects observed with the spring ST->DST transition, there are long-term adverse health effects due to disturbances in sleep and circadian rhythm misalignment throughout DST that are independent of any short-term transition effects. The circadian clock follows sun time and not local clock time.⁵ Introducing DST is equivalent to making people live according to the local clock time of one time zone further east (i.e., Chicago residents have to live according to Boston time). Most studies of health effects of DST utilize longitudinal position in time zone (e.g., comparing western vs eastern edges of the time zone that differ by an hour of sun time within the same local clock time) as a proxy of the year-round temporal misplacement caused by DST to estimate the chronic effects. The later sunrises and sunsets (and resulting sleep and circadian disruption) are associated with multiple negative health outcomes (e.g., obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, cancer, insufficient sleep).^{6,7} The underlying mechanisms for these challenges are chronic, and include dysregulation of melatonin and cortisol contributing to stress, altered metabolism, and inflammation.^{12,13} DST also has adverse effects on neuropsychological function⁸ that are associated with increases in suicides⁹ and traffic accidents¹⁰, despite short-term benefits related to light exposure during evening commutes. Data from a natural experiment confirmed the

detrimental long-term effects of permanent DST on adolescent sleep times and seasonal depression when compared to permanent ST and seasonal DST.¹¹

Data from multiple sources led many scientific and sleep societies in Europe and other areas to conclude that that the health risks of permanent DST would be worse than both the status quo (i.e., changing between DST/ST) and permanent ST¹²⁻¹⁵ Chronic effects of living in DST are not addressed by the statistical methods in this paper. We support the positions of these societies and advocate for permanent ST.

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